

Personal Values and their Effect on Young Adults Pertaining to OTT Platforms

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Abstract: Children grow fast into adults and there is a difference between adults and young adults as defined by Erick Erickson's psychosocial stages of development. According to Erick Erickson and his theory of psychosocial developments in an individual, there are 8 stages of development. One of the stages is intimacy versus isolation in which he speaks about the age of identity explorations, instability, self focus and the age of feeling in-between and possibilities. This study focuses mainly on the aspects of self sufficiency, economic freedom and social responsibility and reliability in young adults in the age group of 18 - 25 years. The study tries to focus on these aspects based on their screen-time interests pertaining to OTT platforms and the kinds of shows/series the young learners indulge themselves in. The study is based on the statistics collected from a personal values survey done through a pilot study on young adults, focusing on questions based on Erick Erickson's psychosocial stages of development. The study focuses on the values on intimacy, relationships and other moral values among the young adults who are influenced by the series/shows/ movies getting released on popular OTT platforms. For the young adults, their interpersonal and social lives are equally important as their virtual lives. The impact created by Netflix series like *Money Heist* or other K-Drama which are much popular among the young adults is such that they tend to influence their lives adversely. The paper tries to study the relation between their screen time and influence of the OTT shows/series on them before and after the pandemic lockdown in 2020 and how these shows have made an impact on their attitudes and lifestyle.

Keywords: young adults, Erick Erickson's theory of Psychosocial development, OTT platforms, personal values, moral values, stages of individual development.

1. INTRODUCTION

Erik Erikson was a 20th century psychologist who analyzed and divided the human experience into eight stages of development. Each stage has a unique conflict and a result. One such stage — intimacy versus isolation — points out the struggle that young adults have as they try to develop intimate, loving relationships. This is the sixth stage of development, according to Erikson. As students pass through these stages, Erikson believes that they gain skills that would help them succeed in future stages. However, if they have trouble attaining these skills, they might struggle.

In the intimacy versus isolation stage, according to Erikson, success means to have a healthy, fulfilling relationship. Failure means experiencing loneliness or isolation. In our paper which is titled "Young Adults and Personal Values : An Analytical Study with Special Reference to OTT Platform Releases and their Effects on the Attitudes of Young Adults".

Here the study mainly focuses on how the young adolescents of today are clinged to social media platforms ranging from Instagram Reels, Facebook and Youtube Videos or Shorts and especially the OTT platforms through which they imbibe a

major share of their personal values, integrity, norms, ethics, etc. Their attitudes have undergone drastic changes as most of them find an alternative virtual world in social media. For some of them, social media handles serve as a relief from the stressful world, and for some others, social media is a world of friends where they pour out their time, soul and energy. For some young adults, the world of Over the Top platforms is like a world of escape, where they find a lot of freedom, relief and fun. This paper is mainly based on Erikson's theory of psychosocial stages of development in which it is believed that in order to continue developing as a healthy individual, adults need to successfully complete each stage of development; otherwise, they'll be stuck and may even be unable to complete the future stages.

Development of an individual's mindset is directly proportionate to his / her maintenance of healthy relationships. Otherwise, the remaining two phases of development may be in jeopardy. Isolation is often the result of a fear of rejection or dismissal. If one is afraid that he will be turned down or pushed away from a friend or potential romantic partner, you may avoid interactions entirely. The age group for the study taken into consideration is 18-25, all the students being college going students.

Trust vs. mistrust is the first stage in Erik Erikson's theory of psychosocial development. This stage begins at birth continues to approximately 18 months of age. During this stage, the infant is uncertain about the world in which they live, and looks towards their primary caregiver for stability and consistency of care. If the care the infant receives is consistent, predictable and reliable, they will develop a sense of trust which will carry with them to other relationships, and they will be able to feel secure even when threatened.

If these needs are not consistently met, mistrust, suspicion, and anxiety may develop. If the care has been inconsistent, unpredictable and unreliable, then the infant may develop a sense of mistrust, suspicion, and anxiety. In this situation the infant will not have confidence in the world around them or in their abilities to influence events.

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Failing to acquire the virtue of hope will lead to the development of fear. This infant will carry the basic sense of mistrust with them to other relationships. It may result in anxiety, heightened insecurities, and an over feeling of mistrust in the world around them.

Consistent with Erikson's views on the importance of trust, research by Bowlby and Ainsworth has outlined how the quality of the early experience of attachment can affect relationships with others in later life.

Autonomy versus shame and doubt is the second stage of Erik Erikson's stages of psychosocial development. This stage occurs between the ages of 18 months to approximately 3 years. According to Erikson, children at this stage are focused on developing a sense of personal control over physical skills and a sense of independence.

Success in this stage will lead to the virtue of will. If children in this stage are encouraged and supported in their increased independence, they become more confident and secure in their own ability to survive in the world.

If children are criticized, overly controlled, or not given the opportunity to assert themselves, they begin to feel inadequate in their ability to survive, and may then become overly dependent upon others, lack self-esteem, and feel a sense of shame or doubt in their abilities.

International OTT platforms like Netflix, Amazon prime video, HBO max, and Disney+ have started to produce their premium and original content with the aim to grow their reach in every possible country; it created lots of opportunities for new filmmakers and production houses. At the same time, these OTTs today produce content which are quite devoid of personal or societal values, but they make their way straight to homes without any censorship. People, youth especially, get access to such content easily because of which the viewership in the OTTs have increased from the lockdown and pandemic in 2020.

The youth today are carried away by the web-series content and movies on OTT platforms which focus on money making and dream about becoming popular and multimillionaires overnight. A survey was conducted among young adults, who were asked some relevant questions based on their use of OTT platforms and similar gadgets. The paper tries to fetch its conclusion partially from established Erickson's theories and from the survey conducted.

Based on the 80 responses which were collected as part of the survey, 47.5% of the respondents held it important to be honest with their families. Most of them belonged to the following age group:

It is quite saddening that the need to be honest among the family is less than 50% among these young adults. When probed about understanding the message of the movies or shows they watch, only 38% of respondents needed to know the exact meaning and message being conveyed through the shows. Otherwise, they could simply pick and watch any movie or show, just to kill time. Most of the respondents came up with OTT platforms like Amazon Prime Video, Netflix, Disney Hotstar, Youtube and other online streams which do not impose any censorship on the content being watched, but sent directly to the screens in homes. 61.3% of the respondents enjoyed watching action and adventures, and 36.3% watched Horror, thriller series or shows. 12.5% of the respondents openly admitted that they watch adult stuff on online streaming platforms.

What genre of movies/shows/ series do you like to watch on the OTT?
80 responses

Some of the favorite shows on OTTs among these youngsters were Money Heist, Stranger Things, Dance, Reality Shows etc. 50% of the respondents claimed that they were greatly influenced by the shows they watched. One of them said, "It has a great impact on my behavior like the way I talk, walk and speak." 46.3% of the respondents spent around 1 to 4 hours watching OTT shows, and 20% spent 5 to 8 hours on OTT at a stretch. Many of them claim that the pandemic and lockdown which followed in 2020, has increased the screen time.

How many hours of TV shows/movies do you access per week through OTT platforms?
80 responses

One of them said, "My screen time increased majorly during the pandemic to about 7-8 hours." As mentioned above, for some of them OTT shows during the lockdown and pandemic had become part of their everyday life. One of them admits, "It had a negative effect on me. I spent most of the hours confined in my room bingeing on shows like there's no tomorrow, sometimes it did feel as if there wasn't. I wanted to finish everything quickly and for that I spent more than 12 hours each day in front of my screen. Also I wear glasses now."

Therefore, we may see the adverse effects OTT and other online streaming platforms have played on the youth of the society, especially after the lockdown and pandemic. It is high time that we make them aware of these adverse consequences.

If let loose, these consequences may even become reasons for any criminal acts, as we have seen in the case of PubG games and crimes attached to them. It is important that the youth of any country understands the values of the nation and personal values which identify them as human beings. This can be achieved by orienting the youth about their usage of OTTs and the time they spend on these online activities.

REFERENCES

- [1] Ahuja R, 'Study of Effects of Web Series & Streaming Content on Indian Youth', *IJCRT* 8:1042-1055.
- [2] Boyd, D. & Bee, H. *Lifespan Development*. Boston: Allyn and Bacon. 2006.
- [3] Blascovich J., Mendes W.B. 'Challenge and threat appraisals: The role of affective cues.' In Forgas J. (Ed.), *Feeling and thinking: The role of affect in social cognition* (pp. 59–82). Cambridge, England: Cambridge University Press.
- [4] Erikson Erik H. *Identity : Youth and Crisis*. W.W. Norton 1968.
- [5] Google Form Response Analysis - <https://docs.google.com/forms/d/1uFvHgVpRCFIU0ltvsT2sQV8aSEBoqU1u-P6vDktr5nY/viewanalytics>